

Reward and Employee Performance during the Covid-19 Pandemic: A Case Study of Fajar University Employees in Makassar City Indonesia

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Abstract:- This study is descriptive of the cauldron to explain the reward and performance of employees in the covid-19 pandemic. Methods of data collection observation and in-depth interviews. The results of the study found ten informants explained that before there was a pandemic covid-19 they got salaries, food allowances, transport allowances, and, structural benefits for those in positions. But since the coronavirus, there has been a reduction in a reward. However, the performance of employees remains good because they know the rewards at Fajar University are still better than other private universities.

Keyword:- Reward, Employee Performance, And Pandemic Covid-19.

I. INTRODUCTION

Higher education institutions in Makassar City consist of public universities and private universities that are quite advanced such as Muslim University, Muhammadiyah University, Fajar University, and Darma Nusantara High School. Fajar University employs many employees and foundation lecturers as well as lecturers of higher education service institutions. In addition, it manages three faculties, namely the Faculty of Economics and Social Sciences, the faculty of engineering, and the graduate faculty. The faculty of economics and social sciences consists of several study programs including management studies, accounting, international relations, communication, and English. While the engineering faculty consists of civil engineering, architectural engineering, and mechanical engineering. The graduate faculty manages master's programs in management, master of communication, and master of environmental engineering. Students of Fajar University are quite a lot, especially the faculty of economics and social sciences. But in the time of pandemic covid-19, there are employee complaints related to their rewards.

Pandemic covid-19 affects learning and reward systems in various companies including higher education institutions. Therefore, the Rector needs to motivate employees by providing a decent reward. Siramiati et. al., (2015) organizations need to reward employees to be motivated to work. The reward needs to be adjusted to the employee's working life. Cassandro, (2008) Rewards that are under workload can improve employee performance. Because rewards can affect employee performance. Reward-based on seniority and work results, based on skills, knowledge, employee experience, (Okwudili 2016). Each company must pay a reward based on the provincial

minimum wage that has been set by the government. A reward is a financial reward and recognition encourages positive behavior that is better performance, (Sudarmanto 2009). Employee performance is influenced by motivation as well as the work environment, (Tahmeem Siddiqi and Sadia Tangem, 2018). This shows that rewards are closely related to employee performance. This means that the better the reward, the better the employee performance. Employee performance is influenced by potential and knowledge skills and skills, Motivation is influenced by attitude and environment, (Mangkunegara 2005). One of the successes of several private universities in Makassar city is due to good reward systems such as the Muslim University of Indonesia, the University of Muhammadiyah, and Fajar University. But since the covid-19 private university has decreased the number of students including Fajar University. Based on this phenomenon, researchers are interested in reviewing the reward and performance of employees of Fajar University in Makassar City.

Fajar Education Foundation has several business units, namely: Fajar newspaper, Graha Pena, Fajaruniversity, Nitro college of financial sciences, FAJAR TV, the hall of them. But the study focused only on researching FajarUniversity employees. This research novelty is coronavirus (covid-19). The reason the research was conducted was to know that the coronavirus (covid-19) affected the economy and reward system in the Company. Formulation of research problems (1). How to reward Fajar University employees in the covid-19 period. (2) How the employees of Fajar University performed during the covid-19 pandemic.

II. THEORETICAL STUDIES

Rewards are very strategic for maintaining the best human resources, (Yokohama, 2007). Every organization needs to reward employees accordingly. Gbervbie, (2011) good reward combination of financial and awards in the form of praise to employees, (Maund, 2001). Rewards are salaries, sales bonuses, overtime, and vacations, (Osibanjo Adeniji et., al 2014). A reward is a reward in return for the work of employees. In determining human resource development rewards and supervisors play an important role in preparing reward system policies, conducting surveys, carrying out work evaluation processes, having employee welfare packages. Employees who get low rewards will look for side jobs to meet the needs of life and family so that they are not optimal at work. Naidu and Satyanarayana (2018) companies must provide decent rewards to reduce employee turnover. Rewarding needs to consider workload, skills, and

competencies. One factor that can increase work motivation is the reward, (Mathis & Jackson 2002). In economic theory, the reward is a payment obtained from various forms of services provided to workers. Employees need to be rewarded so that they can perform well, (Sudarmanto 2009).

Employee performance is the result of work, according to the standards set by the company, (Christopher and Bulah, 2016). Employee performance is the result of work. Employee performance is determined by good ability and work environment by improving rewards, (Pawirosumarto et., al 2017). Employee performance is the planning or program and achievement of policy implementation in realizing the goals, vision goals, and mission of the organization, (Muheriono, 2012). Employee performance is measured from six indicators, namely: quality of work, quantity of work, punctuality, cost efficiency, ability to work, and the ability to build work relationships, (Bernadin and Russell, 1999).

Reward adjustments and job performance evaluations can help managers determine salary increases and bonuses. But in the pandemic covid-19, the company experienced a decrease in turnover. Covid-19 was discovered in Wuhan China in December 2019 caused by a new type of virus, (He et al., 2020). The virus developed around the world and

entered Indonesia in February 2020 and claimed many lives. On March 11, 2020, WHO declared the Covid 19 pandemic a Global Pandemic, (Dong et al., 2020). In anticipation of the spread of covid-19, the Government of Indonesia issued a policy to work from home, (Muliati, 2020). Thus the income of the community decreased, especially small traders so President Jokowi provided monetary assistance for employees whose salaries were below Rp 5,000,000, - and assistance to the poor amounted to Rp 300,000, - / household heads, (Prasetyo., 2020).

III. RESEARCH METHODS

The study is descriptive qualitative with methods of collecting observational data and in-depth interviews. Informant 10 employees of Fajar University. This study examined the rewards and performance of employees in the covid-19 pandemic. Mathis & Jackson (2006) explains that reward is an important factor in people working in an organization. A decent reward is a combination of financial and non-financial to optimize employee contributions, namely better performance, (Gberevbie, 2011). The conceptual framework of this research is based on empirical studies and literature studies and under the problems, formulated presented in the following images:

IV. RESEARCH RESULTS

Informant 1. Smd, Head of The Academic Bureau of Fajar University, age 47 years. Interview Thursday, April 1, 2021. I started working at Fajar University in 2009 until now. Initially, my salary was only Rp 750,000. In 2018 I have finished my S2 education and was promoted as Head of Academic Bureau until now. I got a receipt allowance of Rp 1,500,000 and a salary of Rp 1,500,000 plus Rp 900,000 and transportation allowances of Rp 900,000 plus online communication allowances of Rp 200,000 so the reward I received was Rp 5,000,000. At the end of the year employees and lecturers get a bonus. But since the covid-19 there has been no increase in salary even there is a policy of

the chairman of the foundation to reduce employee rewards. However, I still work well because I am aware of my duties and responsibilities as an employee.

Informant 2. SN, employee, age 42 years. Interview Monday, April 7, 2021. I have worked at Fajar University since 2008 the opening of Fajar University. My salary is only Rp 750,000 and in 2014 my salary was Rp 1,200,000 and in 2018 my salary was Rp 1,500,000 plus Rp 900,000 and transportation allowances of Rp 900,000. In addition, there are online communication allowances of Rp 200,000 so the reward salary I received was Rp 3,500,000. But at the end of the year, we get bonuses that vary in magnitude. Since the covid-19 there has been no increase in salary even

meal allowances and transport allowances is reduced and online communication allowances is removed. Although there is a reduction in rewards I still survive working at Fajar University because my hope in the future will improve if covid-19 is no longer there.

Informant 3, ABM, academic employees, age 45 years. Interview Thursday, April 12, 2021. I started working at Fajar University in 2009 with the status of ordinary employees with a salary of Rp 750,000. In the third year, I was appointed as a permanent employee with a salary of Rp 900,000. In 2018 my salary was Rp 1,500,000 plus Rp 900,000, transportation allowances Rp 900,000, and online communication allowances Rp 200,000 so the reward I received was Rp 3,500,000. But since the covid-19 there has been a reduction in rewards. Nevertheless, I continue to work as usual, and when the government imposes restrictions on our community activities employees work at home. I stayed at Fajar University because it was difficult to find a job.

Informant 4, ND, Secretary of the Faculty of Engineering, age 56. Interview Tuesday, April 15, 2021. I started working in 2008 until now. Initially, I was just a regular employee but in 2017 I was promoted as secretary of the Engineering Faculty and got a structural allowance of Rp 1,500,000. In 2018 my salary was Rp 1,500,000 plus Rp 1,500,000 and transportation allowances of Rp 1,500,000 plus online communication allowances of Rp 200,000. So the reward I received amounted to Rp 5,000,000. However, there is a reduction in a reward. At the end of the year, we get a bonus. I'm still working as usual because it's my job and my responsibility.

Informant 5, Alm finance staff, age 50. I have worked at Fajar University since 2010. The reward I received was Rp 800,000 and I was placed in the administration section but in 2015 I was mutated into the finance department until now with a reward of Rp 1,300,000 and in 2018 my salary was Rp 1,500,000 plus meal allowances, transportation allowances, and online communication allowances so that my reward was Rp 3,500,000. But the coronavirus in the number of students decreased so that there was a reduction in rewards. However, I am still working in the hope that things will improve as Covid-19 no longer exists.

Informant 6, Amr age 40. I worked at Fajar University in 2012. My salary is very minimal Rp 900,000 and placed in the academic section but I am patient the salary will rise as the number of students increases. In 2017 I was placed in the HR section until now. In 2018 my salary was Rp 1,500,000 plus Rp 900,000 and transportation allowances of Rp 900,000 and online communication allowances of Rp 200,000 so the reward I received was Rp 3,500,000. But since covid-19 there has been a reduction in rewards, but I still work as usual because it is a trust given to me and I have to take responsibility for my work.

Informant 7, Stk age 40. I worked at Fajar University in 2013 with a salary of Rp 1,000,000 and was placed in the Faculty of Economics and social sciences. In 2018 the University of Fajar opened a graduate with a master's degree

in communication, a master's in environmental engineering, and a master's in management, and I was promoted as secretary of the graduate program. My salary is Rp 1,500,000 plus the structural allowance of Rp 1,200,000, meal allowances Rp 900,000 plus transport allowances Rp 900,000, and online communication allowances Rp 200,000 so that the reward I received Rp 4,700,000. In addition, at the end of the year, there are bonuses from foundations whose amounts vary. But since the covid-19 there has been no increase in salary even a reduction in existing rewards. I hope that things will improve if the coronavirus no longer exists.

Informant 8, Nhy library staff, age 40. Interview Tuesday, April 27, 2021. I worked at Fajar University since 2008 and was given a salary of Rp 750,000. Although my salary is minimal I still survive because it is difficult to find a job. After all, my education is only the completion of high school, the salary of Rp 1,000,000 and in 2018 my salary is Rp 1,400,000 plus Rp 900,000 and transport allowances Rp 900,000. The online communication allowance is Rp 200,000 so the reward received is Rp 3,400,000. But at the end of the year, there is a bonus from the foundation of Rp 600,000. Since covid-19 there has been a reduction in rewards and I am still working because I enjoy my work.

Informant 9, Nhd, 50-year-old library head. Interview May 3, 2021. I worked at Fajar University since 2009 and was paid Rp 750,000 but I still survived because I hoped that in the future the reward would increase as the number of students increased. In 2014 my salary was Rp 1,300,000 and in 2018 I was already master and promoted as head of the library and got a salary of Rp 1,500,000 and structural allowance of Rp 1,500,000 plus meal allowances of Rp 900,000, transportation allowances of Rp 900,000, and online communication allowances of Rp 200,000 so that my reward was Rp 5,000,000. But since there is a coronavirus there is a reduction in a reward. However, I continue to work in the hope that things will return to normal if the coronavirus no longer exists.

Informant 10, Ilhm, staff of the data and statistics center institute of Fajar Makassar University aged 45 years. Interview on May 6, 2021. I worked at Fajar University in 2013 until now. My salary is Rp 1,300,000. But every two years there is an increase. In 2018 I was already a magister and promoted as head of the data center and statistic institute. My salary is Rp 1,500,000 plus a structural allowance of Rp 1,500,000 and meal allowances of Rp 900,000, and transport allowances of Rp 900,000 plus a credit of Rp 200,000 so the reward I received is Rp 5,000,000. But since the pandemic, there has been a reduction in rewards. Nevertheless, I still survive working at Fajar University because the reward at Fajar University is still better than the reward at other private colleges so I do not intend to leave my job.

V. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

Based on the results of interviews from ten research informants it can be concluded that before there were covid-19 employees of Fajar University received a fairly good reward because in addition to getting a salary also got food allowances and transport allowances and online communication allowances. Likewise, there are positions such as the head of the library and the head of their institution that are given structural allowances of Rp1,500,000. But since the covid-19 the number of students decreased so the chairman of the Foundation issued a policy to reduce employee rewards due to financial deficits. What is reduced is the structural allowance which was Rp 1,500,000 down to Rp 1,000,000. The meal allowances dropped to Rp 400,000. Transport allowances also dropped to Rp 400,000. Not only employees who get a reduction in reward but foundation lecturers are also reduced in reward. However, Fajar University still survives to work well and does not intend to quit their jobs because employees know that the reward at Fajar University is still better when compared to rewards at other private universities. The management of Fajar University is quite good because it is managed professionally by providing a hefty reward to all employees so that employees are still committed to their work. In addition, at the end of the year employees are given year-end bonuses that vary depending on their position. Basa employees are given a bonus of Rp 600,000 and those with positions have bonuses more than that. So in the pandemic covid-19, the performance of Fajar University employees is still good despite the reduction in food allowances, transport allowances, and structural benefits. Online communication allowances are also removed.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Bernadin, H. John dan Russel J. E. A. (1999). *Human Resources Management. Second Edition*. Mc-Hill Inc, Singapore.
- [2.] Cassandro, M. H. (2008). Project manager, HR specialist, ONESTEP compensation: Outline and definitions. HR Guide to the Internet. 2000. www.hr-guide.com/data/G400.htm
- [3.] Christopher, M. N., & Bulah, H. O. (2016). The relationship between total compensation and employee performance in the insurance industry, Case of Mayfair Insurance Company Limited. *Psychology and Behavioral Sciences*, 5(1), 20-36.
- [4.] Dong, Y., Mo, X., Hu, Y., Qi, X., Jiang, F., Jiang, Z., & Tong, S. (2020). Epidemiology of COVID-19 among children in China. *Pediatrics*, 145(6).
- [5.] Gbervbie, D. E. (2011). Leadership, the financial sector and development in Nigeria. *Inkanyiso: Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 3(2), 148-158.
- [6.] GITAHI He, F., Deng, Y., & Li, W. (2020). Coronavirus disease 2019: What we know?. *Journal of medical virology*, 92(7), 719-725.
- [6.] Mangkunegara, Anwar Prabu A. A. 2005. *Corporate Human Resource Management*. PT Remaja Rosdakarya Bandung.
- [7.] Maund, L. (2001). *An Introduction to Human Resource Management Theory & Practice*. Palgrave, Macmillan.
- [8.] Mathis, R.L. & Jackson, J.H. 2002. *Human Resource Management, Books 1 and 2*, Jakarta: Salemba Four Publishers. Jakarta.
- [9.] Muheriono, (2012), *Competency-based performance measurement, revised edition*. PT Rajagrafindo Persada.
- [10.] Muliati, N. K. (2020). The Impact of the Indonesian Economy in Various Sectors Due to Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19). *Widya Accounting and Finance*, 2(2), 78-86.
- [11.] Naidu, A. T., & Satyanarayana, G. (2018). Impact of Compensation on Employee Performance. *Intercontinental Journal of Human Resource Research Review*, 6(4), 1-7.
- [12.] Okwudili, B. E. (2016). *Contemporary issues in Human Resource Management*. PhD Class note.
- [13.] Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike, Abia State, Nigeria.
- [14.] Osibanjo, O. A, Adeniji, A.A, Falola, H. O, & Heirsmac, P.T.(2014). Compensation packages: a strategic tool for employees' performance & retention. *Leonardo Journal of Sciences*, 25, 65-84.
- [15.] Pawirosumarto, S., Pawirosumarto, S., Sarjana, P. K., Sarjana, P. K., Muchtar, M., & Muchtar, M. (2017). Factors affecting employee performance of PT. Kiyokuni Indonesia. *International Journal of Law and Management*, 59(4), 602-614.
- [16.] Prasetyo, E. (2020). Strategic Role of Entrepreneurship in Supporting Four Track Strategy Policy in Indonesia. *Optimum Journal of Economics and Development*, 10, 1-15.
- [17.] Siramiati, N. W., Hadiwidjojo, D., & Rohman, F. (2015) Performance-based compensation affect employee motivation, a satisfaction of employees, and performance of employees (study on private universities in the Province of Bali): conceptual frameworks. *Korea*, 61, 50-5.
- [18.] Sudarmanto. 2009. *Performance and Development of HR Competencies (Theory, Dimension measurement and implementation in organizations)*. Yogyakarta, Student Library.
- [19.] Tahmeem Siddiqi and Sadia Tangem, (2018) impact of work environment, compensation and motivation on the performance of employees in the insurance companies of Bangladesh Southeast Asia Journal of Contemporary Business, Economics, and Law, Vol. 15, Issue 5 (April) ISSN 2289-1560.
- [20.] Yokohama, M. (2007). When to us Employee Incentive Gifts. Retrieved from <http://ezinearticles.com/?when-to-use-employee-incentive-gifts&id=647448>.